

REVIEW ARTICLE

Advances in Cancer Pharmacotherapy

Abstract

Recent advancements in cancer pharmacotherapy, fueled by a deeper understanding of molecular oncology, have shifted focus from traditional chemotherapeutic agents, which often cause systemic toxicity due to their lack of specificity, to more precise approaches like targeted therapies and immunotherapy, offering improved efficacy and reduced adverse effects. This review explores advances in cancer pharmacotherapy including stem cell therapy, targeted therapy, Immunotherapy, nanotechnology therapy, combination therapy, ablation therapy. This review also discusses the challenges in cancer pharmacotherapy such as improving the accessibility of these innovative treatments.

Keywords: *Stem cell therapy, targeted therapy, immunotherapy, nanotechnology, combination therapy, ablation therapy.*

INTRODUCTION

Cancer, a group of diseases that can originate in almost any organ or tissue, occurs when abnormal cells grow uncontrollably, invade surrounding tissues, and potentially spread to other organs. As the second leading cause of death globally, cancer is responsible for approximately 9.6 million deaths annually, accounting for 1 in 6 deaths. Every day, more than 52,900 individuals are diagnosed with cancer, while over 27,000 people succumb to the disease.

ADVANCED PHARMACOTHERAPY

TARGETED THERAPY

Targeted therapy is a type of cancer treatment that targets proteins that control how cancer cells grow, divide, and spread. A primary goal of targeted

therapy is to fight against cancer cells with more accurately and potentially less side effects. Targeted therapy blocks the proliferation of cancer cells by interfering with specific molecules required for tumor development and growth. Targeted therapies, which include mAbs and small molecule inhibitors (SMInhs), have significantly changed the treatment of cancer over the past 15 years.

Targeted cancer agents are broadly classified as either monoclonal antibodies or small molecules.

Monoclonal antibodies are immunoglobulin structure designed to target specific antigens found on the cell surface, such as transmembrane receptors or extracellular growth factors. In some cases, monoclonal antibodies are conjugated to radioisotopes or toxins to allow

specific delivery of these cytotoxic agents to the intended cancer cell target.

Clinical pearl: The names of monoclonal antibodies often end in -mab (eg, rituximab, bevacizumab, trastuzumab).

Monoclonal antibodies are manmade proteins that act like human antibodies in the immune system. There are 4 different ways they can be made and are named based on what they are made of.

Murine: These are made from mouse proteins, and the names of the treatments end in -omab.

Chimeric: These proteins are a combination of part mouse and part human, and the names of the treatments end in -ximab.

Humanized: These are made from small parts of mouse parts of mouse proteins attached to human proteins, and the names of the names of the treatments end in -zumab.

Human: These are fully human proteins, and the names of the treatments end in -umab.

Types of monoclonal antibodies that are used to treat cancer are naked monoclonal antibodies, conjugated monoclonal antibodies, antibody -drug conjugates, radiolabelled antibodies and radioimmunotherapy.

Conjugated monoclonal antibodies

Conjugated monoclonal antibodies are

designed to deliver chemotherapy drugs or radioactive particles directly to cancer cells by binding to specific antigens, acting as a precise delivery system to target and treat cancerous tissues. These mAbs, also known as tagged, labeled, or loaded antibodies, circulate through the body until they attach to the targeted antigens, releasing the toxic substance exactly where it is most needed.

Antibody-drug conjugates (ADCs):

These monoclonal antibodies are linked to potent chemotherapy drugs, enabling targeted treatment. For example, Brentuximab vedotin (Adcetris) is an antibody-drug conjugate (ADC) that targets the CD30 antigen on lymphocytes and is connected to the chemotherapy drug MMAE. Another example is Ado-trastuzumab emtansine (Kadcyla or TDM-1), an ADC that targets the HER2 protein and is attached to the chemotherapy drug DM1.

Radiolabeled antibodies: Radiolabeled antibodies carry small radioactive particles that are directed to cancer cells, delivering radiation precisely where it is needed. This type of treatment, known as radioimmunotherapy (RIT), uses the antibody to locate the target cells, allowing the attached radiation to effectively impact both the target and nearby cells.

Naked monoclonal antibodies

Naked mAbs are antibodies that have no drug or radioactive material attached to them. They work by themselves. These are the most common type of mAbs used to treat cancer. Most naked mAbs attach to antigens on cancer cells, but some work by binding to antigens on other, non-cancerous cells, or even free-floating proteins. Some examples of monoclonal antibody drugs are listed below:

Drugs	Target
Transtuzumab	HER2 receptor
Pertuzumab	HER2 receptor
Bevacizumab	VEGF-A
rituximab	CD20 antigen

Small molecules are usually designed to interfere with the enzymatic activity of target protein. They can penetrate the cell membrane to interact with targets inside a cancer cell.

Clinical pearl: The names of small molecule drugs are often end in –mib (for protease inhibitors) or –nib (for kinase inhibitors), such as bortezomib, osimertinib, and vemurafenib.

As of 2024, the US FDA approved 80 small molecule therapeutic protein kinase inhibitors for cancer, that targets about two dozen different protein kinases and seven of these were approved in 2023. Of the approved drugs, thirteen target protein serine/ threonine protein kinases, four are directed against dual specificity protein kinases (MEK1/2), twenty block nonreceptor protein – tyrosine

kinases, and 43 inhibit receptor protein-tyrosine kinases. The data indicate that 69 of these drugs are prescribed for the treatment of neoplasms.

Advantages and Disadvantages of small molecule inhibitors

Compared to other drugs, small molecule drugs are easier and less costly to synthesize and prepare, and they are often administered orally, providing greater convenience for patients with fewer side effects. However, these drugs primarily target proteins like enzymes or receptors, which can limit their effectiveness against membrane and secretory proteins. Moreover, the influence of metabolism makes it difficult to fine-tune the dosage of small molecule inhibitors to achieve optimal efficacy. A significant challenge remains in targeting undruggable proteins, which has impeded the development of drugs for many oncogenes.

Challenges

With the advancement of these technologies, proteins previously deemed undruggable are increasingly being reclassified as "yet-to-be-drugged" targets, broadening the scope of small molecule inhibitors. However, the future of small molecule inhibitors still presents significant challenges. For example, patients treated with EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitors like Gefitinib, Erlotinib, Afatinib, and Dacomitinib face a 50-60% likelihood of developing resistance within a year. Therefore, it is

crucial to continue exploring alternative therapeutic strategies. Additionally, challenges remain in achieving breakthroughs for targeting highly homologous protein families and undruggable targets. Furthermore, ensuring the safe dosage and metabolic stability of small molecule inhibitors is vital to maintaining their safety and efficacy within the therapeutic window. Some examples of small molecule inhibitor drugs are listed below:

Drug	Target
osimertinib	EGFR
Larotrectinib	NTRK
Entrectinib	NTRK1/2/3, ROS1, and ALK fusion proteins
Sotorasib	KRAS G12C

Stem cell therapy

Stem cells, found in the bone marrow, are undifferentiated cells with the potential to become any body cell and are being explored as a safe and effective cancer treatment in experimental trials. Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), derived from bone marrow, fat, and connective tissue, are currently being tested for their potential in regenerating damaged tissues.

Types of stem cells

Pluripotent stem cell

Embryonic stem cells (ESCs) from the inner mass of embryos can become any cell type except those in the placenta. The 2006 discovery of Yamanaka factors enabled the creation of induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) from adult cells, which, like ESCs, have broad differentiation potential but avoid ethical concerns. Both hematopoietic ESCs and iPSCs are now used to generate effector T cells, natural killer (NK) cells, and for preparing anti-tumor vaccines.

Adult stem cell

Adult stem cells (ASCs) used in tumor therapy include hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs), which can form all mature blood cells and are FDA-approved for treating multiple myeloma and leukemia, mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), which aid in tissue repair and regeneration, and neural stem cells (NSCs), which generate

neurons and glial cells for treating primary and metastatic tumors.

Cancer stem cell

Cancer stem cells (CSCs), arising from normal stem or progenitor cells through epigenetic mutations, play a role in tumor growth, metastasis, and recurrence. Stem cell therapies leverage mechanisms such as homing to specific niches, tumor-tropic effects, and paracrine factor secretion to target tumors. Strategies include HSC transplantation, MSC infusion, and immune cell generation, though challenges such as tumorigenesis, drug resistance, and immune responses remain. Continued research is needed to enhance safety and efficacy before widespread clinical use.

Some examples of stem cells therapy drugs are listed below:

Stem cell therapies	Examples	Indication
Pluripotent stem cell	iPSC	Prostate cancer
Adult stem cell	MSC- INF	Ovarian tumor
Cancer stem cell	Venetoclax	AML

Ablation therapy

Ablation therapy is a minimally invasive treatment that uses heat, cold, or electric current to destroy cancerous tumors without requiring major surgery. This procedure is performed by inserting specialized probes through the skin, guided by imaging, to directly target and destroy the tumor. There are different types of ablation therapy, including cryoablation

(freezing the tumor), radiofrequency ablation (heating the tumor with radio waves), microwave ablation (using electromagnetic waves to burn the tumor), and ethanol ablation (injecting alcohol to damage cancer cells). Ablation is often used for treating small tumors in organs like the liver, kidneys, and lungs, especially when surgery is not an option. The treatment has several advantages, such as minimal pain, shorter recovery time, and the ability to be combined with other therapies. However, side effects may include abdominal pain, infection, and liver function abnormalities, although serious complications are rare. Newer techniques like NanoKnife are also being developed to improve the effectiveness of ablation, particularly for challenging tumors.

Nanotechnology

Recent advancements in cancer nanotechnology offer promising opportunities for targeted drug delivery, with nanoparticles (10-100 nm) emerging as effective therapeutics. These nanoparticles can carry multiple functional molecules, such as drugs, peptides, proteins, and nucleic acids, and utilize both passive and active targeting to enhance drug accumulation in cancer cells while reducing normal cell toxicity. Additionally, nanoparticles can bypass drug resistance mechanisms, like the P-glycoprotein efflux pump, potentially overcoming drug resistance and

improving therapeutic efficacy.

Nanoparticles for Tumor Targeting and Delivery

Nanoparticles used for anticancer drug delivery can be made from a variety of materials, including polymers, dendrimers, liposomes, silica, carbon nanotubes, and metals such as iron oxide and gold. So far, almost all the nanoparticle delivery systems which have been approved by the FDA or are currently in clinic trials are based on polymers or liposomes.

Examples of nanomaterials currently being investigated in clinical trials for various applications to improve therapeutic delivery, diagnostics, radiation therapy, and imaging modalities

1. Polymeric nanoparticles

Polymers for nanoparticle preparation are typically classified into natural (e.g., heparin, dextran) and synthetic (e.g., PEG, PLA) types, with key requirements including biocompatibility, biodegradability, and functionalizability. Polymeric nanoparticles generally consist of a hydrophobic core for drug entrapment and a hydrophilic shell for stabilization. Drugs can be loaded either by physical entrapment or chemical conjugation, with linker stability crucial for controlled release. Additionally, dendrimers, with their highly branched structures, offer precise control over size, shape, and functionalization, making them valuable for drug delivery and imaging applications.

2. Liposomal nanoparticles

Liposomes, spherical particles with phospholipid bilayers ranging from 25 nm to 10 μm , have been explored for drug delivery since their discovery by Bangham. Although unmodified liposomes face limitations due to rapid clearance by macrophages, second-generation polymer-coated liposomes can significantly extend their blood circulation times from minutes to up to 3 days.

3. Gold and iron oxide nanoparticles

Recent advances in nanotechnology have led to the development of new anti-cancer drug delivery systems. Gold nanoparticles, known for their narrow polydispersity and potential in

in vivo pharmacokinetic studies due to their low natural concentrations in the body, show promise but raise concerns about long-term toxicity. Gold nanorods, which generate heat when exposed to near-infrared (IR) lasers, offer potential in photothermal therapy by targeting and destroying tumors while sparing healthy tissue. Iron oxide nanoparticles, used clinically for MRI imaging, are being explored as drug carriers with the added benefit of targeted delivery via external magnetic fields.

4. Metallic nanoparticles

Metal nanoparticles (NPs) are submicron-scale structures composed of pure metals or their compounds, such as gold, silver, zinc, cerium, iron, and silica, in forms like oxides, hydroxides, sulfides, phosphates, fluorides, and chlorides. The method of production significantly affects the size and shape of these nanoparticles, which can be synthesized or functionalized through various physical, chemical, and biological techniques. These techniques often utilize biological or chemical reagents as reducing and/or capping agents on the NP surface. Metal NPs have been extensively studied in research due to their rapid and scalable synthesis, green synthesis using plant extracts or natural products, and their ease of functionalization for drug delivery, as the drug is coated on the NP surface rather than being entrapped as in liposomal or polymeric systems. However, two major challenges with

metal NPs include their high surface-to-charge ratio, which leads to the formation of a protein corona that can mask drug delivery and activity, and the potential for metal accumulation in tissues or organs, posing unknown long-term toxicity risks and concerns about crossing the blood-brain barrier with harmful side effects.

5. Silica nanoparticles

Silica NPs are mesoporous within a diameter range of 2–50 nm, and these mesoporous silica NPs (MSNP) are widely used for drug delivery, catalysis, adsorption, separation, etc. Two natural agents, curcumin and colchicine, were loaded on MSNPs, and efficacy was tested against several cancer cell lines, in vitro, (breast cancer cell MCF-7, colon carcinoma HCT-116 cells, lung cancer A-549 cells) where maximum efficacy was obtained against HCT-116 cells with an $IC_{50} < 5 \mu\text{g/ml}$ showing apoptotic death with increased p53, caspase-3, and Bax expression, but inhibited Bcl-2 expression [85]. Biomass-derived GQDs combined with hollow MSNPs (hMSNPs) are used for fluorescent imaging and dual treatment of cancer via drug delivery and PDT. Although the addition of hMSNPs creates more toxicity, the GQDs-hMSNs solved dual purpose—drug delivery using fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) as a mock drug, and PDT treatment by using the GQDs as a photosensitizer which can induce singlet oxygen-mediated high ROS. Combined gas-

radiotherapy (GT-RT) from a gold-capped MSNP was possible due to the loading of NOSH-aspirin which is a dual-donating cytotoxic gas producer—nitric oxide and hydrogen sulphide. X-ray irradiation along with drug delivery creates a unique GT-RT reduced subcutaneous and orthotopic hepatocellular carcinoma tumours with high biocompatibility.

6. Carbon nanotubes

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs), discovered in the late 1980s, are allotropes of carbon composed entirely of sp² hybridized carbons, belonging to the fullerene family of hollow carbon structures. They are categorized as either multi-walled CNTs (MWCNTs, 2–100 nm) or single-walled CNTs (SWCNTs, 0.4–2 nm). SWCNTs and MWCNTs naturally align into cylindrical shapes with varying radii and chiral angles through van der Waals forces, giving them unique structural, chemical, and physical properties such as high mechanical strength, low density, and excellent conductivity. SWCNTs consist of a single cylindrical graphene layer, while MWCNTs are composed of concentric graphene sheets. These CNTs, with lengths ranging from 1 to 100 nm, are formed by rolling up graphene sheets, which are one-atom-thick layers made of benzene-type hexagonal carbon atoms. For example, PEGylated SWCNTs, linked with an ester, demonstrated superior antitumor efficacy and longer circulation time in breast cancer studies compared to both Taxol and

PEGylated paclitaxel. Additionally, folic acid-conjugated CNTs with raloxifene (commonly used to treat osteoporosis in postmenopausal women) target cancer cells via folate receptors, enhancing the efficacy of raloxifene with an IC₅₀ of 43.5 µg/ml. These findings suggest that CNTs hold promise as carriers for anticancer drug delivery. However, the toxicity of CNTs varies; for instance, SWCNTs showed greater toxicity than MWCNTs, impairing the phagocytosis of alveolar macrophages at a low dose of 0.38 mg/cm². Toxicity also increases with the length of CNTs, as macrophages struggle to engulf CNTs longer than 800 nm, leading to higher inflammation and cytotoxicity. Additionally, the functionalization of CNTs with various chemicals affects their accumulation and toxicity in different organs; for example, taurine-functionalized MWCNTs accumulated in the liver for 3 months, whereas diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA)-functionalized SWCNTs were rapidly cleared from the bloodstream within 3 hours without causing deposition or toxicity

Challenges

Despite promising advancements in nanotechnology-based cancer diagnosis, only a few have progressed to clinical trials due to challenges in reliability, large-scale production, device development, and potential toxicity. Ensuring consistent and reliable detection, producing cost-effective and stable nanoprobes,

creating user-friendly NP-based devices, and addressing nanoparticle toxicity in systemic administration are key hurdles that need to be overcome for clinical translation.

Combination therapy

Combination therapies in oncology have seen significant progress, with recent studies highlighting their efficacy in improving patient outcomes. For instance, the IMbrave150 study showed that Atezolizumab and Bevacizumab (T + A) significantly extended median overall survival (mOS) in Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC) patients compared to sorafenib. In 2023, novel combinations, including Tafenlar and Mekinist for pediatric low-grade gliomas, and zolbetuximab with mFOLFOX6 for advanced gastric cancer, demonstrated substantial benefits, highlighting ongoing advancements in cancer treatment strategies.

Combined therapy with immune checkpoint inhibitor

Since 2006, the FDA has approved 90 cancer combination therapies, notably integrating immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) with other treatments. This includes frequent combinations like Nivolumab and Ipilimumab, and various chemotherapies. The latest guidelines emphasize combining immunotherapy with other modalities for first-line treatment across multiple cancers, showing improved survival rates and efficacy in recent studies. Additionally, new therapies and clinical

trials are advancing, exploring novel combinations and modalities such as oncolytic viruses with ICIs.

Combined therapy in small molecule inhibitor

The FDA has approved 22 small molecule drug combinations for cancer treatment, demonstrating their frequent use in clinical practice. Recent guidelines highlight the tailored application of these combinations based on cancer types and molecular markers, such as combining EGFR inhibitors with anti-angiogenic drugs for NSCLC or HER2 inhibitors with chemotherapy for HER2-positive breast cancer. Preclinical studies and clinical trials further support the efficacy of these combinations, showing improved survival and reduced adverse effects in various cancers.

Combined use of anti-angiogenic drugs

The FDA has approved 14 anti-angiogenic drug combinations, highlighting their role as essential components in cancer treatment. These combinations, such as Bevacizumab with Atezolizumab or chemotherapy, are increasingly part of first-line regimens for various cancers. Recent studies and clinical trials emphasize the efficacy of these combinations, with promising results in treating cancers like NSCLC, CRC, and HCC, and suggest that combining anti-angiogenic drugs with other therapies continues to offer significant

clinical benefits.

Advantages, disadvantages and challenges of combination treatment

Despite their benefits, combination therapies face challenges, including strict eligibility criteria, potential drug interactions, and increased risk of adverse events. For example, the talazoparib + enzalutamide combination is limited to patients with HRR gene mutations, and the pembrolizumab + chemotherapy regimen requires high PD-L1 expression. Adverse effects and increased costs also pose concerns, highlighting the need for better drug selection, dosage determination, and predictive biomarkers to guide treatment and manage costs.

Immunotherapy

Immunotherapy is a cancer treatment that boosts the immune system's ability to recognize and attack cancer cells. Normally, the immune system detects and eliminates abnormal cells, including cancer cells, but some cancers can evade immune responses. Cancer cells may alter their genetic makeup to become less detectable, produce proteins that deactivate immune cells, or modify surrounding tissues to inhibit immune attacks. Immunotherapy works by enhancing the immune system's capacity to overcome these obstacles and more effectively target and destroy cancer cells. Types of immunotherapy are Cancer vaccines, CAR- T cell therapy and immune checkpoint inhibitors.

Cancer vaccines

Cancer vaccines have been studied for 40 years with limited success, evolving from early bacterial approaches to modern therapies that deliver tumor antigens with adjuvants. Current vaccines under investigation include peptide, RNA, DNA, tumor cell, viral, and dendritic cell-based vaccines.

Protein or peptide vaccines use specific proteins from cancer cells to trigger an immune response.

DNA and RNA vaccines introduce genetic material to enhance the immune system's ability to target cancer cells.

Whole cell vaccines utilize entire cancer cells to stimulate an immune response.

Dendritic cell vaccines involve growing immune cells with cancer cells to train the immune system to attack cancer.

Virus vaccines use modified viruses to deliver cancer antigens, with T-VEC

being a notable treatment for

melanoma by destroying cancer cells and aiding immune detection.

Cancer vaccines have faced numerous challenges in achieving clinical success, largely due to the intricate coordination required between various immune components, including antigen-presenting cells, T cells, natural killer cells, and tumor-associated myeloid cells. Despite these obstacles and a history of setbacks, advancements in understanding antigen immunogenicity, immune cell exhaustion, and the integration of combination therapies offer new hope for their potential inclusion in effective cancer treatment strategies.

CAR- T CELL THERAPY: A LIVING DRUG

CAR T cell therapy is an innovative cancer treatment that utilizes a patient's own immune cells, specifically T cells, to fight cancer. In this process, T cells are extracted from the blood and genetically modified to express chimeric antigen receptors (CARs), which enable them to target specific antigens found on cancer cells. Once engineered, these CAR T cells are multiplied in a lab and reintroduced into the patient's bloodstream, where they seek out and destroy cancer cells. This therapy has shown significant success in treating certain blood cancers, including lymphomas and leukemias, by targeting antigens like

CD19 and BCMA on B cells.

Some examples of CAR-T cell therapy drugs are listed below:

Drug	Target
Tisagenlecleucel	CD19
Axicabtagene ciloleucel	CD19
Brexucabtagene autoleucel	CD19
Lisocabtagene maraleucel	BCMA
Idecabtagene vicleucel	BCMA
Ciltacabtagene autoleucel	BCMA
NexCAR19	CD19

CAR T-cell therapy is a type of treatment in which a patient's T cells are genetically engineered in the laboratory so they will bind to specific proteins (antigens) on cancer cells and kill them. (1) A patient's T cells are removed from their blood. Then, (2) the gene for a special receptor called a chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) is inserted into the T cells in the laboratory. The gene encodes the engineered CAR protein that is expressed on the surface of the patient's T cells, creating a CAR T cell. (3) Millions of CAR T cells are grown in the laboratory. (4) They are then given to the patient by intravenous infusion. (5) The CAR T cells bind to antigens on the cancer cells and kill them.

cancer.gov

Immune checkpoint inhibitors

Immune checkpoints are regulatory proteins that help control immune cell

activity, preventing excessive immune responses that could damage healthy tissues. However, cancer cells can exploit these checkpoints to suppress immune system activity, allowing them to evade destruction. In cancer therapy, inhibitors targeting key immune checkpoints like PD-1, PD-L1, and CTLA-4 have been developed to restore the immune system's ability to recognize and attack tumor cells. some examples of immune checkpoint inhibitors are given

Abbreviations:

- BCMA: B- cell maturation antigen
- PD-1: Programmed Death-1
- CTLA-4: Cytotoxic T-Lymphocyte Antigen-4
- PD-1L: Programmed Death- Ligand 1
- EGFR: Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor
- NTRK: Neurotropic receptor tyrosine kinase fusion proteins

below:

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FAD approved drugs	Targets
Pembrolizumab	PD-1
Ipilimumab	CTLA-4
Nivolumab	PD-1
Atezolizumab	PD-L1

Conclusion

Pharmacotherapy	Advantages	Disadvantages	Challenges	Examples
Monoclonal antibodies	High specificity for cancer cells.	High cost, antibody related side effects	High production cost, antibody related side effects, low penetration efficiency, long half life with risks of adverse effects.	Transtuzumab, pertuzumab, bevacizumab, rituximab.
Small molecule inhibitors	Simpler and less expensive synthesis and preparation process	Limited inhibitory effects on membrane proteins and secretory proteins.	Undruggable proteins solution, covalent modulation, allosteric inhibition.	Osimertinib (tagrisso) Larotrectinib Entrectinib Sotorasib
Stem cell therapy	Graft-versus-tumor effect: in some cases, the stem cell transplant can directly fight cancer.	Risk of infection, risk of new cancer, delayed growth and development, reproductive problems	Tumor heterogeneity, resistance to therapy, immune evasion.	
Nanotechnology	Targeted drug delivery, improved drug solubility, controlled drug	Complex manufacturing, variable biodistribution, limited long term data	Reliability, large scale production, device development, potential toxicity.	Iron oxide nanoparticles (such as Fe ₃ O ₄)

	release, enhance imaging, overcome resistance.			
Combination therapy	Increased efficacy, reduced drug resistance, lower drug doses, minimizes metastasis	Increased toxicity, complex drug interaction, higher cost, increased treatment complexity.	Strict eligibility criteria, potential drug interaction, increased risk of adverse events.	Atezolizumab with bevacizumab
Ablation therapy	Minimal pain, shorter recovery time.	Side effects may include abdominal pain, infection, liver function abnormalities	rare	
CAR-T cell therapy	Highly specific targeting, durable response, personalized treatment.	Cost and accessibility, risk of release, complex manufacturing process.	Antigen escape, manufacturing scalability, managing side effects, immunosuppression.	Tisagenlecleucel, Axicabtagene ciloleucel, Brexucabtagene autoleucel, Idecabtagene maraleucel, Ciltacabtagene autoleucel, NexCAR19
Cancer vaccines	Effective at preventive tumor occurrence, potential to stimulate	Efficacy is inconsistent due to individual antigen variability and immune	Enhancing vaccine individual immunogenicity.	Bacillus calmette-Guerin (BCG) Sipuleucel-

	long term immune memory for lasting protection against cancer recurrence.	microenvironment interference.		T (Provenge) Gardasil Gardasil-9 Hepatitis B (HBV) vaccine (HEPLISAV-B)
Immune checkpoint inhibitors	Long lasting response, less frequent dosing, restores immune function.	High cost, potential for immune exhaustion, not effective for all patients.	Identifying biomarkers, overcoming resistance, managing immune related toxicities	Pembrolizumab Ipilimumab Nivolumab Atezolizumab

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